

PROJECT-BASED WRITING DALAM PEMBELAJARAN MENULIS AKADEMIK MAHASISWA

Nur Shabrina Reznani¹, Bambang Sulisty², Nurhasanah³

¹Manajemen, STIE Dwi Sakti Baturaja, Jalan Prof. Dr. Hamka Nomor 541-A, Sukaraya, Baturaja Timur, Ogan Komering Ulu, Sumatra Selatan, Indonesia

^{2,3}Pendidikan Bahasa Indonesia, Universitas Baturaja, Jalan Ratu Penghulu Nomor 2301, Karang Sari, Baturaja, Tj. Baru, Baturaja Timur, Ogan Komering Ulu, Sumatra Selatan, Indonesia

¹e-mail: shabrinareznani23@gmail.com

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Abstrak

Penelitian bertujuan untuk mengukur efektivitas *project-based writing* (PBW) terhadap keterampilan menulis akademik mahasiswa. Metode penelitian yang digunakan adalah praeksperimen dengan rancangan penelitian *one group pretest-posttest design*. Populasi penelitian berjumlah 60 mahasiswa STIE Dwi Sakti Baturaja. Teknik pengambilan sampel yang digunakan adalah sampel jenuh sehingga keseluruhan populasi dalam penelitian dijadikan sampel penelitian. Teknik pengumpulan data menggunakan tes berupa *pretest* dan *posttest*. Pengolahan data dilakukan dengan perhitungan uji-t dengan bantuan program aplikasi SPSS 20. Hasil penelitian menunjukkan bahwa penerapan PBW efektif terhadap keterampilan menulis akademik mahasiswa. Nilai rata-rata *posttest* mengalami peningkatan dari nilai *pretest*. Berdasarkan hasil penelitian, maka disimpulkan bahwa penerapan PBW efektif meningkatkan keterampilan menulis akademik mahasiswa Manajemen pada mata kuliah wajib kurikulum Bahasa Indonesia.

Kata Kunci: efektivitas pembelajaran; *project-based writing*; menulis akademik.

Abstract

The research aimed to measure the effectiveness of *project-based writing* (PBW) on students' academic writing skills. The research method used pre-experimental with a one-group pretest-posttest design. The research population consisted of 60 students of STIE Dwi Sakti Baturaja. The sampling technique used a saturated sample so that the entire population in the research was used as the research sample. Data collection techniques used tests in the form of pretest and posttest. Data processing was carried out by calculating the t-test with the help of the SPSS 20 application program. The results showed that the application of PBW was effective on students' academic writing skills. The average value of the posttest has increased from the pretest value. Based on the results of the research, it was concluded that the application of PBW was effective in improving the academic writing skills of Management students in compulsory Indonesian language curriculum courses.

Keywords: learning effectiveness; *project-based writing*; academic writing.